

Annual Report

A new path towards hydrogen

2023

anemel.eu

European
Innovation
Council

Co-funded by
the European Union

About ANEMEL

ANEMEL is a project, funded by the European Commission, focused on making green hydrogen from plentiful and sustainable resources, such as saline and waste waters.

To do this, the project will develop an electrolyser (a system that uses electricity to break water into hydrogen and oxygen) powered by green energy sources. This device will make use of non-critical raw materials within all its basic parts, including electrocatalysts and membranes.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

<u>I. WP 1 - Catalysts</u>	3
<u>II. WP 2 - Membranes</u>	5
<u>III. WP3 - Cells</u>	7
<u>IV. WP6 - DEC</u>	9
<u>V. WP9 - Portfolio</u>	11

WP1 - CATALYSTS

Catalysts accelerate chemical reactions. In our case, we look for catalysts that accelerate water splitting – the transformation of water into its two components, hydrogen and oxygen. Currently, the main challenge of ANEMEL is creating catalysts that are free of critical raw materials, which will boost the overall sustainability of our process and devices. In the first year of the project, we've focused on the study of catalysts based on abundant metals such as nickel, iron, and se, mostly.

Electrolysers – the devices that split water into hydrogen and oxygen – consist of two separate electrodes, the anode and the cathode. In the anode, the reaction that takes

“As part of the European Innovation Council, we get access to training in technology transfer, which is a great opportunity to learn how to turn our technological advances into marketable products, maybe even creating a start-up.”

place is water oxidation, therefore the formation of oxygen gas. On the other hand, the cathode witnesses water reduction – also known as hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The teams at ANEMEL work on different catalysts for water oxidation and HER, since each of the reactions has different chemical requirements. For the anode, our partners study different nickel and iron salts, especially oxides, sulfides, and selenides, because we've observed they improve factors such as conductivity and stability of the electrode.

Additionally, nickel and iron are cheap and abundant metals. Our teams also work on nickel catalysts – mainly nickel nitride – as accelerators of the HER, as

well as other compounds such as manganese oxide. Last but not least, we also research bifunctional catalysts, which accelerate both the formation of hydrogen and oxygen. Currently, these catalysts count on cobalt, classified as a critical raw material because it comes, mostly, [from conflict zones and overexploited mines in low-income countries](#). Alternatively, we're researching nickel–iron borides, which offer a more sustainable solution, but this is a very early-stage line of research. Besides sustainability, another advantage of the catalysts developed by ANEMEL is simplicity – we don't rely on complex

coordination compounds; instead, we work with binary salts, such as chalcogenides, nitrides, and borides, easy to synthesise and crystallise. Our teams work on adjusting the proportion of metals towards finding the perfect “recipe” – a sustainable solution to split salty water and wastewater efficiently.

ANEMEL also looks into long-term sustainability – indeed, it’s one of the project’s core values. In that sense, our teams investigate the efficiency and reliance of catalysts comparing them with [industry standards](#), including platinum–carbon and silver–silver chloride electrodes. Such

benchmarks check the current required to split water, as well as measure the amount of hydrogen produced. Moreover, these studies survey stability – measuring how the electrode degrade over continuous catalytic cycles. During the first year of the project, our researchers have observed a very good performance of nickel, iron, and manganese in conditions that mimic seawater. In the future, the goal is lowering the working pH to less basic conditions, ideally outperforming state-of-the-art solutions based on noble metals, which are both expensive and scarce.

Getting rid of CRMs

Critical raw materials (CRMs) are specific minerals, metals, and other raw materials that are considered crucial to the economic, industrial, and technological advancements of a region. On top of economic importance, the "critical" status is also connected to potential supply risks, as well as the lack of substitutes for certain applications – the case of many metals, especially rare earths like lanthanides. [Almost ten years after publishing its first list of CRMs](#), in 2023 the European Union has officially launched the “[Critical Raw Materials Act](#)”, which will ensure secure and sustainable supply chains.

WP2 - MEMBRANES

Membranes make the heart of our electrolyzers. And ANEMEL investigates new membrane materials free from fluorinated “forever chemicals”, with increased conductivity and scalability than traditional solutions. Like in the case of catalysts, one of the most important hurdles is making membranes that withstand the extreme conditions created by seawater – mostly related to a highly saline, highly oxidising media. Moreover, membranes must showcase better durability and recyclability to meet our sustainability objectives.

In an electrolyser – a device that splits water into hydrogen and oxygen – membranes play two main roles, beyond just physically separating the electrodes. Membranes are usually semipermeable structures, which enable the movement of ions and liquids but block

“Our long-term dream is to produce hydrogen surpassing 100% electrical efficiency, which is theoretically possible and will reduce costs, as well as enable a global cooling effect, a very attractive alternative at the moment.”

gases. This is important, because the ions formed in the electrodes must move freely across the membrane – to reach the opposite side and complete the chemical reactions in water splitting. On the other hand, the separation of gases ensures that, once formed, hydrogen and oxygen don’t mix, which ensures both safety – it’s otherwise an explosive mixture – and quality of the product. Since membranes normally withstand extremely reactive conditions, they’re traditionally made of fluorinated polymers, including Nafion and Teflon, because [the carbon–fluorine bonds in their structures constitute the strongest simple bonds in organic chemistry](#).

However, the the long-term stability of fluorinated polymers is a double-edged

sword. Although this ensures a high resistance to the attack of oxidising species and radicals, it creates a conflict related to recyclability and sustainability.

Fluorinated chemicals have been popularly baptised as “[forever chemicals](#)”, because of [their extreme biopersistence and bioaccumulation, both of which reportedly lead to harmful health effects](#). Therefore, at ANEMEL we’re moving away from fluorine, exploring other options with long-term stability – and without the pollution problems. Our researchers have found inspiration in some polymers used in fire protection, such as aromatic polymers including polybenzimidazole, among others. Additionally, our partners

are developing innovative engineering methods to increase the conductivity and the mechanical properties of membranes – and compensate the consequences of cutting out fluorinated compounds.

Among the most exciting discoveries of this first year, ANEMEL researchers have observed that making composites of polymers and cerium oxide improves the stability of membranes, especially against radical attacks. On top of that, the results show that cerium oxide also promotes the regeneration of hydroxide ions, one of the key drivers of the water oxidation reaction. Furthermore, preliminary tests have helped identify new functional groups that also improve stability, especially in alkaline media, such as isoindolinium – a type of nitrogen heterocycles. Next steps will involve implementing these technologies into scalable syntheses and manufacturing processes, to fabricate fibres and membranes with long-term stability, which will improve the overall sustainability of the electrolyser.

Technology free of “forever chemicals”

PFAS – poly-fluorinated alkyl substances – is a term that encompasses several thousands of industrial chemicals, with a carbon chain decorated with different amounts of fluorine atoms. Since the popularisation of DuPont’s Teflon™ and “non-stick” kitchenware in the 1940s and 1950s, PFAS became ubiquitous – which eventually became a problem. Although not all PFAS are equally contaminant, the high resistance of carbon–fluorine bonds makes these compounds into very persistent pollution, linked to problems such as bioaccumulation and diseases like kidney cancer. The case of fluorinated “forever chemicals” is featured, for example, in the blockbuster movie “Dark Waters”, starring Mark Ruffalo and Anne Hathaway.

Nowadays, both policymakers and polymer manufacturers work together towards finding cleaner alternatives to PFAS. The European Union and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) lead the way with one of the most ambitious and restrictive regulations, which aims to prohibit most “forever chemicals” by 2035.

WP3 - CELLS

We haven't started studying biocatalysis – a “cell” refers to the basic electrocatalytic structure, with the electrodes, the electrolyte, the membrane, and eventually an encasing system that holds everything together. This ANEMEL team combines the contributions of Work Packages 1 and 2, working on catalysts and membranes respectively, to create a functional electrolytic cell.

The inner structure of an electrolytic cell is, basically, like a sandwich. It counts on a series of layers for support, catalysis, and ion transport, and both the order and the quality of the ingredients really matter. In the cathode – where hydrogen is produced – the catalyst, composed of nickel and iron, is deposited onto a porous transport layer made of felt, often “doped” or coated with other materials that improve conductivity. Traditionally, electrolyzers used cathodic transport layers with gold and titanium – both rather scarce metals. ANEMEL focuses on replacing the rare and expensive ingredients in the sandwich with more abundant options, including solutions like nickel foams and sulfur-doped nickel felt. For the anode – the site of water oxidation – our alternatives for transport layers include nickel foam and phosphorus-doped nickel felt as well as simple carbon paper, all of

Cutting-edge techniques

Spray coating is a scalable state-of-the-art technique used in the manufacturing of electrolytic cells, as well as the up-and-coming perovskite solar cells. The production process involves spraying a thin and uniform layer of functional materials, such as electrolytes and catalysts, onto a substrate – which eventually yields the different components of “sandwiched” electrolyzers. Once mastered, spray coating offers several advantages, including a precise control of the layer thickness and a uniform coverage and coating – even on complex surfaces. Moreover, it's got a true potential for scalable production processes both cost-effective and sustainable.

which deposit our iron-based catalysts, as an alternative to state-of-the-art solutions based on platinum and cobalt, both critical raw materials (CRMs). In this first year of ANEMEL, researchers have focused on benchmarking and characterisation of electrolytic cells, which included aspects such as performance, activity, and durability – all linked to the overall long-term sustainability of the device. Among other challenges, the presence of chlorine ions in seawater creates competitive reactions, including the generation of highly corrosive and toxic chlorine gas. Magnesium cations, also naturally present in seawater, could clog the catalytic electrode too.

We work together with the rest of the researchers in ANEMEL to develop more selective solutions, ready for the conversion of seawater into green hydrogen. Moreover, we're developing new automated techniques for spray coating – the technology used to deposit the catalyst onto the porous transport layers. One of the goals is reducing the reliance on fume hoods and gloveboxes, promoting procedures that work in open-air, facilitating the scale-up process and reducing the technological challenges of air-sensitive chemistry. Eventually, this contributes to our long-term goal of delocalising and democratising hydrogen production – ensuring green hydrogen becomes a commodity easily accessible all around the world.

Furthermore, to improve the characterisation of the catalytic processes in water splitting, ANEMEL is developing a new type of experimental cell that will allow *in operando* measurements without stopping the reaction. The setup will provide “live” access to the solution in the electrolyser, giving our researchers a unique opportunity to study the process with different spectroscopic techniques. Some of the ongoing work has been presented in published peer-reviewed papers, as well as international conferences, an impressive steppingstone for the first year of the ANEMEL project.

WP6 – DEC

Communication is key to EU-funded projects. Otherwise, the exciting results from our laboratories never reach the general public – the fundamental funders of research. Additionally, our dissemination activities help us connect with collaborators, both in academia and industry, to catalyse cooperation and establish new potential partnerships in the long run.

During the first year of ANEMEL, our main focus was the establishment of a strong and coherent brand strategy – to cement the project’s presence. Among other things, this involved the creation of a logotype and a corporate colour palette, which laid the basis for the design of all our other communication materials in print and online. We created a starting kit including an infographic, an animated video, and a brochure, all available for free online. The idea behind was communicating both the importance of green hydrogen for the European economy, as well as the novelty of the ANEMEL approach, which will eventually allow to manufacture hydrogen from impure water sources, delocalising and democratising hydrogen production. On top of all that, we established an online presence for the project – with a website and different social media profiles on platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn. We use these channels to communicate and disseminate stories periodically, always following the Communications Plan, refreshed every few months to adapt to the evolving needs of a project like ours.

Additionally, our Work Package presented the project at different events, including important policymaking events in Brussels like #RePowerEU. The idea behind these dissemination and communication actions is reaching potential partners in academia and industry, as well as developing strong relationships with policymakers in Brussels and the

Hydrogen & its rainbow of colours

‘Green’ hydrogen is really a brand, created by industry to categorise the different manufacturing strategies and their environmental impact. Although in reality hydrogen is an odourless and colourless gas, for most industries it comes in many different colours – green, gray, blue, pink, purple – which symbolise different sources and production processes. For example, ‘grey’ hydrogen comes from methane cracking, which not only relies on fossil fuels but also requires tremendous amounts of energy – overall it’s quite contaminant. We explain more details in one of our communication blogposts, ‘[The colours of hydrogen](#)’, available on www.anemel.eu.

Member States, to ensure the deployment of the hydrogen economy is supported by

“Our aim is to develop intellectual property that catalyses the commercialisation of electrolysers, ready to manufacture green hydrogen from dirty waters.”

relevant regulations and a long-term funding strategy. We collaborated closely with other portfolio projects within our same EIC Pathfinder challenge “Novel Routes to Green Hydrogen Production”.

Soon, we will also start working on innovation and exploitation activities, to ensure that our technology is transferred to industry successfully. Despite the low technology readiness levels (TRLs), the aim of ANEMEL is to develop intellectual property that catalyses the commercialisation of

electrolysers, ready to manufacture green hydrogen from dirty waters. It’s important that we protect that, and elaborate an extensive commercialisation plan as we advance towards higher TRLs.

WP9 - PORTFOLIO

The portfolio activities ensure collaboration between ANEMEL and the rest of the projects funded within the EIC Pathfinder challenge “Novel Routes to Green Hydrogen Production”, including strategies like photocatalysis, biocatalysis, and many more. This innovative initiative kicked-off with a meeting in Brussels shortly after the start of the projects, in October 2022. Then, the projects discussed the different priorities and potential partnerships, and drafted a roadmap for synergic communication and innovation activities in the years to come.

One of the outstanding priorities was participation in events, in collaboration with the portfolio projects and the European Innovation Council (EIC). This includes three events during this first year, as well as preparations for a portfolio meeting, which will take place in Tarragona, Spain, in October 2023. Firstly, invited by the EIC, ANEMEL attended an event in Brussels that reinforced the strong pledge of the European Union to the hydrogen economy. As part of the EU's strategy to become the first climate-neutral continent, Commissioner Mariya Gabriel committed to collaborations that will catalyse innovation in hydrogen, to create jobs and tackle the most urgent energy challenges. The event gathered over 300 leading stakeholders and experts in hydrogen technology, including researchers, innovators, investors, and policymakers.

Tackling hydrogen from different angles

ANEMEL works in the sustainable synthesis of green hydrogen from seawater and wastewater. But the projects in the portfolio go beyond production processes, such as electrocatalysis, photocatalysis, and biocatalysis, and also study other important issues, including novel sources of hydrogen, like biomass. Additionally, some projects look into the industrial applications of green hydrogen for the decarbonisation of the European economy. Our sister project H2STEEL, for example, studies the uses of hydrogen in the manufacture of steel – an industry that currently contributes to the climate crisis considerably. The decarbonisation of industrial processes with hydrogen will eventually eradicate a big portion of carbon dioxide emissions, towards a more sustainable future.

Furthermore, ANEMEL representatives also attended the Financial Times Hydrogen Summit, which took place in London in June 2023. This event brought together business executives alongside leaders in finance, government, and policymaking, and devised discussions to provide key insights on reaching the full potential for green hydrogen.

ANEMEL also co-organised an in-person workshop to discuss the importance of sustainable sourcing of water in the generation of green hydrogen, as well as the production of clean chemicals, renewable fuels, minerals, and more. The event took place at the premises of the Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG-RTD) of the European Commission in Brussels, on 8 and 9 June 2023, and was attended by over 150 people, including researchers, industry leaders, and policymakers. Other members of the portfolio, including projects like GH2 and ELOBIO, also attended the event, showcasing the importance of cross-collaboration for the success of our initiatives on green hydrogen.

Moreover, at ANEMEL we also took charge of different dissemination and communication activities to promote the portfolio of projects within the 'Green Hydrogen' EIC challenge. We established internal communication channels across the different projects and taskforces, all setup in Microsoft Teams, a platform that enables collaborations across institutions, including the exchange of messages, files, and the organisation of online meetings. We also designed and develop a website for the portfolio, publicly available now on: www.eichydrogen.eu. The main objective of this online platform is to showcase the mission and vision behind the portfolio of projects, as well as showcase the names, logos, and descriptions of the different initiatives. As an initial approach, we also included a series of frequently asked questions (FAQs) to provide a better overview of the funding strategy of the EIC, and most importantly of the industry value of green hydrogen as a clean power source in the transition to a zero-carbon economy in Europe.

